

PROPER d- LUCKY LABELING ON SPECIAL GRAPHS

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Abstract

In this paper we investigate the existence of Proper d-lucky labeling for some special graphs.

Keywords: Proper d-Lucky Labeling, Twig, Barycentric, Cycle, Kite.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of graph labeling was introduced by Rosa in 1967 [8]. Mirka Miller et.al., [7] introduced the concept of **d-lucky labeling**. Let $l: R(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ be the vertex labels of G which is assigned by positive integers. Define $c(u) = d(u) + \sum_{r \in N(u)} l(r)$, [where $d(u)$ is the degree of u and $N(u)$ is the open neighbourhood of u].

A Labeling l is expound to be D-lucky if $c(u)$ and $c(r)$ are not equal. For every couple of adjacent vertices u and r in G .

Indicate the D-lucky number of a graph G by $\eta_{dl}(G)$, which is the smallest positive k in order that G has a D-lucky labeling with $\{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ as the set of labels. Esakkiammal et.al., [6] introduced the concept of **Proper d-lucky Labeling**.

A D-lucky labeling is called proper if $l(u) \neq l(r)$ for every adjacent vertex u and r . The proper D-lucky number of a graph is the least positive integ k such that G has a Proper D-lucky labeling with $\{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ as the set of labels and is denoted by $\eta_{pdl}(G)$. Bala et.al., introduced the concept of Triplicate **Graph of Cycle** C_n .

Let $V = \{v_i \cup v'_i \cup v''_i / 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and edge set $E = \{v'_{i+1}v_i \cup v_{i+1}v'_i \cup v'_iv''_{i+1} \cup v''_iv'_{i+1} / 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\} \cup \{v_nv'_n \cup v'_nv_1 \cup v'_nv''_1 \cup v''_nv'_1 / 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Clearly, $TG(C_n)$ has $3n$ vertices and $4n$ edges.

Bala et.al., [2] introduced the concept of **Triplicate Graph of kite** $TG(\text{kite})_n$. Let $V = \{v_j \cup v'_j \cup v''_j \cup u_i \cup u'_i \cup u''_i / 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and edge set $E = \{v'_{i+1}v_i \cup v_{i+1}v'_i \cup v'_iv''_{i+1} \cup v''_iv'_{i+1} / 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\} \cup \{v_nv'_1 \cup v'_nv_1 \cup v'_nv''_1 \cup v''_nv'_1\} \cup \{v'_1u_1 \cup v_1u'_1 \cup v'_1u''_1 \cup v''_1u'_1\} \cup \{u_iu'_{i+1} \cup u''_iu_{i+1} \cup u'_iu''_{i+1} \cup u''_iu'_{i+1} / 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\}$.

Clearly, $TG(\text{kite})_n$ has $6n$ vertices and $8n$ edges. Bala et.al., [1] introduced the concept of **The Barycentric Extended Duplicate Graph of Twig** $EDG(T_n)$. Let $V = \{v_j \cup v'_j / 1 \leq i \leq n + 2\} \cup \{b_i \cup r_i / 1 \leq i \leq n + 1\} \cup \{b'_i \cup r'_i \cup b''_i \cup r''_i \cup u_i \cup u'_i \cup w_i \cup w'_i /$

$2 \leq i \leq n + 1\} \cup \{s_1\}$ and edge set $E = \{v_i b_i \cup r_i v_{i+1} \cup v'_i r_i \cup b_i v'_{i+1} / 1 \leq i \leq n + 1\} \cup \{v_i b''_i \cup v'_i r''_i \cup v'_i b'_i \cup v'_i r'_i \cup b'_i u_i \cup r'_i w_i \cup b''_i u'_i \cup r''_i w'_i / 2 \leq i \leq n + 1\} \cup \{v_2 s_1 \cup v'_2 s_1\}$.
 Clearly, $EDG(T_n)$ has $12n + 7$ vertices and $12n + 6$ edges.

2. MAIN RESULT

In this section we investigate the existence of Proper D-Lucky Labeling on Triplicate Graph of cycle, Triplicate Graph of kite and Barycentric Extended Duplicate Graph of Twig.

THEOREM: 2.1

Triplicate Graph of cycle $TG(C_n)$ admits proper d-Lucky labeling with $\eta_{dl}(TG(C_n)) = 2$.

Proof:

The Triplicate Graph of Cycle C_n , denoted by $TG(C_n)$ has the vertex set $V = \{v_i \cup v'_i \cup v''_i / 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and edge set $E = \{v'_{i+1} v_i \cup v_{i+1} v'_i \cup v'_i v''_{i+1} \cup v''_i v'_{i+1} / 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\} \cup \{v_n v'_n \cup v'_n v_1 \cup v'_n v''_1 \cup v''_n v'_1\}$.

Clearly, $TG(C_n)$ has $3n$ vertices and $4n$ edges.

To prove $TG(C_n)$ is Proper d-lucky, define the function $l: V(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ to label the vertices as follows:

For, $1 \leq i \leq n$

$$l(v_i) = l(v''_i) = 1, l(v'_i) = 2$$

Clearly, it has $l(v_i) \neq l(v_j)$ for any two adjacent vertices of $TG(C_n)$.

From the structure of the $TG(C_n)$, it is clear that the degrees of the vertices are as follows:

For, $1 \leq i \leq n$

$$d(v_i) = d(v''_i) = 2, d(v'_i) = 4$$

Using the relation $c(v_i) = d(v_j) + \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} l(v_j)$ we obtain the d-lucky number as follows

For, $1 \leq i \leq n$

$$c(v_i) = c(v''_i) = 6, c(v'_i) = 8$$

Clearly,

$$(i) c(v_n) \neq c(v'_n), c(v'_n) \neq c(v_1), c(v'_n) \neq c(v''_1), c(v''_n) \neq c(v'_1)$$

$$(ii) \text{ For, } 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$$

$$c(v'_{i+1}) \neq c(v_1), c(v_{i+1}) \neq c(v'_1), c(v'_i) \neq c(v''_{i+1}), c(v''_i) \neq c(v'_{i+1})$$

Since any two adjacent vertices of $TG(C_n)$ are not equal. $TG(C_n)$ admits proper d-lucky labeling with $\eta_{dl}(TG(C_n)) = 2$.

EXAMPLE: 2.1

Proper d-lucky labeling $TG(C_n)$ is shown in the figure.

THEOREM: 2.2

Triplicate Graph of kite $TG(\text{kite})_n$ admits proper d-Lucky labeling with $\eta_{dl}(TG(\text{kite})_n) = 2$.

Proof:

The Triplicate Graph of kite $(\text{kite})_n$, denoted by $TG(\text{kite})_n$ has the vertex set $V = \{v_j \cup v'_j \cup v''_j \cup u_i \cup u'_i \cup u''_i / 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ and edge set $E = \{v_{i+1}v_i \cup v_{i+1}v'_j \cup v'_i v''_{i+1} \cup v''_i v'_{i+1} / 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\} \cup \{v_n v'_1 \cup v'_n v_1 \cup v'_n v''_1 \cup v''_n v'_1\} \cup \{v'_1 u_1 \cup v_1 u'_1 \cup v'_1 u''_1 \cup v''_1 u'_1\} \cup \{u_i u'_{i+1} \cup u'_i u_{i+1} \cup u'_i u''_{i+1} \cup u''_i u'_{i+1} / 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\}$.

Clearly, $TG(\text{kite})_n$ has $6n$ vertices and $8n$ edges.

To prove $TG(\text{kite})_n$ is Proper D-lucky, define the function $l: V(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ to label the vertices as follows:

For, $1 \leq i \leq n$

$$l(v_i) = l(v_i'') = l(u_i) = l(u_i'') = 1, l(v_i') = l(u_i') = 2,$$

Clearly, it has $l(v_i) \neq l(v_j)$ for any two adjacent vertices of $TG(\text{kite})_n$.

From the structure of the $TG(\text{kite})_n$, it is clear that the degrees of the vertices are as follows:

(i) $d(v_1) = d(v_1'') = 3, d(v_1') = 6$

(ii) For, $2 \leq i \leq n$

$$d(v_i) = d(v_i'') = 2, d(v_i') = 4$$

(iii) For, $1 \leq i \leq n - 1$

$$d(u_i) = d(u_i'') = 2, d(u_i') = 4$$

(iv) $d(u_n) = d(u_n'') = 1, d(u_n') = 2$

Using the relation $c(v_i) = d(v_i) + \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} l(v_j)$ we obtain the d-lucky number as follows

(i) $c(v_1) = c(v_1'') = 9, c(v_1') = 12, c(u_n) = c(u_n'') = 3, c(u_n') = 4$

(ii) For, $2 \leq i \leq n$

$$c(v_i) = c(v_i'') = 6, c(v_i') = 8$$

(iii) For, $1 \leq i \leq n - 1$

$$c(u_i) = c(u_i'') = 6, c(u_i') = 8$$

Clearly,

(i) $c(v_n) \neq c(v_n'), c(v_n'') \neq c(v_1), c(v_n') \neq c(v_1''), c(v_n'') \neq c(v_1')$

(ii) For, $1 \leq i \leq n - 1$

$$c(v_{i+1}') \neq c(v_1), c(v_{i+1}'') \neq c(v_1'), c(v_i') \neq c(v_{i+1}''), c(v_i'') \neq c(v_{i+1}')$$

$$c(u_1') \neq c(u_{i+1}'), c(u_i') \neq c(u_{i+1}'), c(u_i'') \neq c(u_{i+1}''), c(u_i'') \neq c(u_{i+1}')$$

(iii) $c(v_1') \neq c(u_1), c(v_1) \neq c(u_1'), c(v_1'') \neq c(u_1''), c(v_1'') \neq c(u_1')$

Since any two adjacent vertices of $TG(\text{kite})_n$ are not equal. $TG(\text{kite})_n$ admits proper d-lucky labeling with $\eta_{dl}(TG(\text{kite})_n) = 2$.

EXAMPLE: 2.2

Proper d-lucky labeling $TG(kite)_4$ is shown in the figure.

THEOREM: 3.3

The Barycentric Extended Duplicate Graph of Twig $EDG(T_n)$ admits proper d-Lucky labeling with $\eta_{dl}(EDG(T_n)) = 2$.

Proof:

The Barycentric Extended Duplicate Graph of Twig $EDG(T_n)$, denoted by $EDG(T_n)$ has the vertex set $V = \{v_j \cup v_j' / 1 \leq j \leq n + 2\} \cup \{b_i \cup r_i / 1 \leq i \leq n + 1\} \cup \{b_i' \cup r_i' \cup b_i'' \cup r_i'' \cup u_i \cup u_i' \cup w_i \cup w_i' / 2 \leq i \leq n + 1\} \cup \{s_1\}$ and edge set $E = \{v_i b_i \cup r_i v_{i+1} \cup v_i' r_i' \cup b_i v_{i+1}' / 1 \leq i \leq n + 1\} \cup \{v_i b_i'' \cup v_i' r_i'' \cup v_i'' b_i'' \cup v_i'' r_i'' \cup b_i' u_i \cup r_i' w_i \cup b_i'' u_i' \cup r_i'' w_i' / 2 \leq i \leq n + 1\} \cup \{v_2 s_1 \cup v_2' s_1\}$.

Clearly, $EDG(T_n)$ has $12n + 7$ vertices and $12n + 6$ edges.

To prove $EDG(T_n)$ is Proper d-lucky, define the function $l: V(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ to label the vertices as follows:

(i) For, $1 \leq i \leq n + 2$

$$l(v_i) = l(v'_i) = 1$$

(ii) For, $2 \leq i \leq n + 1$

$$l(b'_i) = l(b''_i) = l(r'_i) = l(r''_i) = 2$$

(iii) For, $1 \leq i \leq n + 1$

$$l(b_i) = l(r_i) = 2$$

(iv) For, $2 \leq i \leq n + 1$

$$l(u_i) = l(u'_i) = l(w_i) = l(w'_i) = 1$$

(v) $l(s_1) = 2$

Clearly, it has $l(v_i) \neq l(v_j)$ for any two adjacent vertices of (T_n) .

From the structure of the (T_n) , it is clear that the degrees of the vertices are as follows:

(i) $d(v_1) = d(v_{n+2}) = d(v'_1) = d(v'_{n+2}) = 1, d(v_2) = d(v'_2) = 5, d(s_1) = 2$

(ii) For, $3 \leq i \leq n + 1$

$$d(v_i) = d(v'_i) = 4$$

(iii) For, $2 \leq i \leq n + 1$

$$d(b_i) = d(b''_i) = d(r_i) = d(r''_i) = 2,$$

$$d(u_i) = d(u'_i) = d(w_i) = d(w'_i) = 1$$

(iv) For, $1 \leq i \leq n + 1$

$$d(b_i) = d(r_i) = 2$$

Using the relation $c(v_i) = d(v_j) + \sum_{v_j \in N(v_i)} l(v_j)$ we obtain the d-lucky number as follows

(i) $c(v_1) = c(v_{n+2}) = c(v'_1) = c(v'_{n+2}) = 3, c(v_2) = c(v'_2) = 15, c(s_1) = 4$

(ii) For, $3 \leq i \leq n + 1$

$$c(v_i) = c(v'_i) = 12$$

(iii) For, $2 \leq i \leq n + 1$

$$c(b'_i) = c(b''_i) = c(r'_i) = c(r''_i) = 4,$$

$$c(u_i) = c(u'_i) = c(w_i) = c(w'_i) = 3$$

(iv) For, $1 \leq i \leq n + 1$

$$c(b_i) = c(r_i) = 4$$

Clearly,

(i) $c(v_2) \neq c(s_1), c(v'_2) \neq c(s_1)$

(ii) For, $1 \leq i \leq n + 1$

$$c(v_i) \neq c(b_i), c(r_i) \neq c(v_{i+1}), c(v'_i) \neq c(r_i), c(b_i) \neq c(v'_{i+1})$$

(iii) For, $2 \leq i \leq n + 1$

$$c(v_i) \neq c(b'_i), c(v_i) \neq c(r'_i), c(v'_i) \neq c(b'_i), c(v'_i) \neq c(r'_i), c(b'_i) \neq c(u_i), c(r'_i) \neq c(w_i),$$

$$c(b''_i) \neq c(u'_i), c(r''_i) \neq c(w'_i)$$

Since any two adjacent vertices of $EDG(T_n)$ are not equal. $EDG(T_n)$ admits proper d-lucky labeling with $\eta_{dl}(EDG(T_n)) = 2$.

EXAMPLE: 3.3

Proper d-lucky labeling $EDG(T_n)$ is shown in the figure.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have confirmed the existence of Proper d-Lucky Labeling on Triplicate Graph of Cycle, Triplicate Graph of Kite and Barycentric Extended Duplicate Graph of Twig.

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